

Oil Spills Impacts on Environmental Sustainability: A Case Study of Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

This study investigated the impact of oil spills in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State Nigeria over a period of two decades 2003-2023. The techniques of Remote Sensing and Geographic Information system was adopted for the study. The dataset used were Landsat images and historical oil spill data of the study area. The images were corrected for atmospheric and geometric distortions. Four remote sensing indices were adopted. These are Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Land Surface Temperature (LST), Normalized Difference Built-Up Index (NDBI). They were subjected to Spatial pattern analysis in the ArcGIS 10.5 software environment. The temporal dynamics of the indices revealed that, NDVI values ranged from -0.12 to 0.68 in 2003, -0.19 to 0.76 in 2013, and -0.17 to 0.63 in 2023 while NDWI ranged from -0.56 to 0.19 in 2003, -0.64 to 0.31 in 2013, and -0.52 to 0.29 in 2023. The NDBI range was from -0.48 to 0.39 in 2003, -0.48 to 0.29 in 2013, and -0.44 to 0.31 in 2023. These result revealed that oil spill susceptibility changed significantly in the study area over time. It was observed that the spill that was absent in 2003 spread to four areas towards the North East in 2013, and to fifteen areas toward the South East in 2023. The oil spill index was evaluated between 2003 and 2013 and inferred a mix of increase and a little decrease in oil spill susceptibility across different regions in the study area. It was concluded that there is an imminent worsening of environmental conditions or an escalation in factors contributing to oil spill risks across the study area. A continuous periodical environmental impact assessment that will provide environmental protection, the safety of the inhabitants of the location and for improvement in oil spill responses was recommended.

Keywords: Environment, Geospatial Techniques, Impact, Oil Spill, Susceptibility.

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INTRODUCTION

Crude oil is a naturally occurring liquid located underneath the earth's surface and can be converted into fuel [1]. It is a mixture of hydrocarbons [2]. However, the extraction process due to poor management has led to oil spills. An oil spill is the intentional or unintentional release of liquid petroleum hydrocarbon into the environment. Many oil spill incidents occur due to ageing infrastructure, equipment failure, operational accidents, sabotage, and theft [3]. The dangers associated with oil spills are numerous and could make life unbearable for the inhabitants of impacted regions. It is a common saying that a shared problem is half solved. Hence, to address solutions to the problems of oil spills, periodic impact assessment with proper data analysis and presentation is needed.

The remote sensing device effectively determines the location and size of oil spills since it covers the region of interest quickly and thoroughly [4]. According to the National Aeronautics and Space Administration, geographic information systems (GIS) are useful tools for combining spatial data

from many sources, such as field surveys, GPS, and remote sensing, to provide a comprehensive overview of the situation. The utilization of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) has improved the capacity to detect alterations on the surface of the Earth. The Normalized Difference Vegetation (NDVI) is a spectral index that can be used to identify long-term variations in the coverage and condition of vegetation [5]. NDVI is a tool used to measure the greenness of vegetation, and its density, as well as assess changes in plant health [6]. The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) introduced by McFeeters, is one of the most commonly used water indices to detect open surface water bodies [7]. It is effectively used for mapping and detecting surface water bodies [7]. In the context of oil spills, NDWI was used to identify oil-contaminated water bodies.

Land surface temperature (LST) is the radiative skin temperature of the land as determined by solar radiation [8]. It is a measurement of the temperature at which certain locations on the earth's surface would feel hot to touch [6]. When assessing oil spills, LST was used to find regions where there are very high temperatures, which could mean that oil is present.

One spectral index that makes it possible to extract and quantify sealed surfaces and built-up regions from satellite imagery is the Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) [9]. It details the degree of land cover change and urbanization in an area. Areas with high human activity levels may be more vulnerable to oil spills; this makes it useful for oil spill detection.

The oil spill index maps assist stakeholders in identifying vulnerable areas that could be impacted by oil spills, help decision-makers comprehend the effects of oil spills on the ecosystem, and enable the visualization of complicated spatial relationships. Stakeholders can then decide how to reduce negative effects on the environment.

Obio/Akpor Local Government Area (LGA) in Rivers State has had repeated incidents of oil spills because of the region's considerable oil extraction activities, according to the joint investigation reports of Shell Petroleum Development Company Nigeria Limited. Furthermore, oil spills have the potential to destroy the ecosystem if left unchecked or poorly managed [10]. The high consequences of oil spills are making life in this region increasingly intolerable, and several communities in the area still suffer from the harmful impacts of oil spills [11]. The residents of Obio/Akpor Local Government Area have cried out for assistance regarding the frequent oil spills, to Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), humanitarian organizations, and state and local governments. Therefore, it is necessary to properly analyze data and offer information on this matter. To investigate the extent, severity, and impact of these spills on environmental parameters such as vegetation, waterbodies, land surface temperature, and built-up areas, a need for thorough geospatial evaluation was necessary and conducted systematically in this research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Various studies have been done on oil spill-related topics. For instance, [12] used multi-endmember spectral mixture analysis (MESMA) and statistical method to determine the detrimental impact of oil spills on vegetation, [13] interest was on the impact of the spill on vegetation based on the frequency and quantity of spill. [14] examined specifically the recovery pattern of vegetation after the spill, while [15] provided a quantitative and geographical study on the causes of the spill such as attacks (interdictions) on Nigerian oil pipelines. [16] did experimental research by conducting soil sample tests to determine the impact of oil spills on soil quality. [17] and [18] worked on detecting and tracking oil pipeline leaks and contaminated locations using multispectral data. On the other hand, [19] focused on the health implications of oil spills. [1] were interested in how oil spill tampers with the food chain while [20] expressed the lapses in the legal action imposed on oil and gas companies that contaminate the environment.

Though most studies only looked at the impact of oil spills on vegetation, after reviewing all of these studies and more, this study adopted the technique of using a geospatial approach by integrating environmental remote sensing indices to assess the impact of oil spills on vegetation, waterbodies, built-up environments, and surface temperature. This study's methodology is unique in that it developed a robust way to integrate the weighted criteria of NDVI, NDWI, LST, and NDBI into one Oil Spill Index map. This ensures that the spatial representation accurately captures the combined

influence of these parameters on oil spill assessment. Other research works related to this study used different methods.

The Study Area

The study are (Figure 1). Obio-Akpor Local Government Area is situated geographically between Latitudes 4°45'N and 4°55'N and Longitudes 6°55'E and 7°05'E. According to [21], Obio/Akpor LGA is bordered to the west by Emohua LGA, to the east by Oyigbo LGA, to the south by Port Harcourt LGA, and to the north by Ikwerre LGA. Obio Akpor LGA is one of the 23 local governments in Rivers State, which is located in what is known as the south southern part of Nigeria, Niger Delta Region. Rumuodo-Maya is home to its administrative centre. The Port Harcourt metropolis comprises the LGAs of Eleme, Port Harcourt, and Obio-Akpor [21]. Obio-Akpor is one of the four local governments dominated by the Ikwerres. Fishing, farming, lumbering, and hunting are the region's ancestral occupations. It had 464,789 residents in 2006, 487,751 in 2015, and 540,308 in 2020, according to estimates. Construction, engineering, civil service, administration, manufacturing, mining, sand dredging, printing, public service, etc. are among the new occupations that have emerged in this region as a result of greater urbanization brought on by the growing population [22]. The research area's equatorial location is near the equator, where typical temperatures range from 25 to 28 degrees Celsius and yearly precipitation ranges from 2000 to 2500 millimetres between April and October. Due to its latitudinal location, the region's high temperatures throughout the year generate increased humidity [21,23]. According to [21], the local vegetation typical of the Niger Delta includes mangrove forests, raffia palm groves, tropical rain forests, and mangrove areas along the shore [21,23].

Figure 1 Map of Nigeria Showing Rivers State showing the Study Area
Source: 2023 maps of world.com & Ministry of Land & Housing Rivers State.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The data acquired for this research are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The Adopted Data and their Attributes

Data	Source	Year	Resolution	Relevance
LANDSAT 8 OLI/TIR LANDSAT 7 TM	United States Geological Survey (USGS)	2023, 2013 2003	30 m 30 m	For remote sensing indices calculation
Administrative map	Rivers state ministry of lands and survey.	2023	1:17000	Extract the boundary of the study area
Coordinates of oil spill points in the study area	Shell Plc. Yearly Spill Incident Data	2023, 2022 2021, 2020 2019, 2012		For validation of results

The acquired data were corrected for radiometric and geometric corrections for the purpose of converting the digital numbers in the Landsat imagery to reflectance values and removal of atmospheric interference. Landsat imagery spectral bands- Red, Green, NIR(near-infrared), SWIR (short-wave infrared) were used for the calculation of NDVI, NDWI, and NDBI needed with the thermal band for the calculation of Land Surface Temperature (LST). These required bands were stacked together into a single image file using ArcGIS 10.5 software. The Normalised Differential Vegetation Index NDVI, Normalised Differential Water Index NDWI, and Normalised Differential Built-up Index NDBI were calculated using the raster calculator in the ArcGIS 10.8 software environment from the formulae in Table 2.

Table 2. Indices Calculation

Index	Formulae	Landsat 7	Landsat 8
NDVI	$\frac{NIR-Red}{(NIR+Red)}$	$\frac{band\ 4 - band\ 3}{band\ 4 + band\ 3}$	$\frac{band\ 5 - band\ 4}{(band\ 5 + band\ 4)}$
	$\frac{Green-NIR}{(Green+NIR)}$	$\frac{band\ 2 - band\ 4}{band\ 2 + band\ 4}$	$\frac{band\ 3 - band\ 5}{(band\ 3 + band\ 5)}$
NDWI	$\frac{SWIR-NIR}{(SWIR+NIR)}$	$\frac{band\ 5 - band\ 4}{band\ 4 + band\ 4}$	$\frac{band\ 6 - band\ 5}{(band\ 6 + band\ 5)}$

Note: Index values typically range from -1 to 1. Higher NDVI values indicates denser and healthier vegetation and lower indicates otherwise. Higher NDWI values indicates water bodies and lower values indicating non-water features and higher NDBI values indicating built-up areas and lower values indicating non-built-up areas.

LST calculation: The thermal infrared bands of Landsat 8 and Landsat 7 imagery from 2023, 2013, and 2003 respectively were used to retrieve LST. The thermal infrared bands (Band 10 for Landsat 8 and Band 6 for Landsat 7) were converted to top-of-atmosphere (TOA) by converting the digital numbers to TOA spectral radiance using sensor radiometric calibration coefficients.

$$TOA(L) = ML * Q_{cal} + AL \quad (1)$$

where:

M_L = Band-specific multiplicative rescaling factor from the metadata ($RADIANCE_MULT_BAND_x$, where x is the band number), Q_{cal} = corresponds to band 10, A_L = Band-specific additive rescaling factor from the metadata ($RADIANCE_ADD_BAND_x$, where x is the band number).

The TOA spectral radiance values were converted to brightness temperature (T) using Planck's Law and the thermal band wavelength using equation 2.

$$Bt = \left(\frac{K_2}{\ln\left(\frac{K_1}{L_\lambda}\right) + 1} \right) - 273.15 \quad (2)$$

Where:

T is the brightness temperature, K_1 and K_2 are band-specific thermal conversion constants, L_λ is the TOA spectral radiance.

The proportion of vegetation Pv was calculated using equation 3:

$$Pv = \left(\frac{NDVI - NDVI_{min}}{NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Subsequently, the land surface emissivity (e) was calculated using

$$e = 0.004 \times Pv + 0.986 \quad (4)$$

After the emissivity-corrected land surface temperatures were estimated in degrees Kelvin, the values were converted to degrees Celsius for easy comprehension. This conversion was achieved using the relation in equation 5

$$LST(^{\circ}C) = LST(K) - 273.15 \quad (5)$$

AHP method was applied for weighting the sensitivity of NDVI, NDWI, LST, and NDBI to oil spill. An AHP matrix was constructed comparing each criterion to every other criterion. Comparisons were made using Saaty's 9-point scale, where 1 indicates equal importance and 9 indicates extreme importance of one criterion over another. As part of the AHP process, the raw comparison matrix was normalized to derive ratio scale priority vectors. Normalization was achieved by dividing each value in a criterion's column by the sum of the column. This converted the comparisons to a proportional ratio scale while maintaining their relativity. The normalization process was applied to each column of the comparison matrix. This enabled priority vectors to be extracted that represented the relative weights or priorities of each criterion proportional to the others.

After assigning weights to NDVI, NDWI, NDBI, and LST for the development of an oil spill index, reclassification of these variables was done before integrating them. Reclassification helps standardize the scales of different variables to ensure comparability and consistency. Since NDVI, NDWI, NDBI, and LST have different measurement ranges and units, reclassification enables harmonization by converting them into common classes or categories. The reclassification interval was assigned a rank weight ranging from 1 to 5 (low to high) corresponding to their influence on oil spills. Classes with a high likelihood of sensitivity were designated with a rank of 5, while those expected to have little or no impact were assigned a rank of 1.

An AHP matrix was constructed comparing each criterion to every other criterion. Comparisons were made using Saaty's 9-point scale, where 1 indicates equal importance and 9 indicates extreme importance of one criterion over another.

Table 3. Saaty Scale for Various Elements Comparison

Scale	Judgment of preference	Description
1	Equally important	Two factors contribute equally to the objective
3	Moderately important	Experience and judgment slightly favour one over the other
5	Important	Experience and judgment strongly important favor one over the other
7	Very strongly important	Experience and judgment strongly important favor one over the other
9	Extremely important	The evidence favouring one over the other is of the highest possible validity
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate preference between adjacent scales	When compromised is needed

Source: [24]

As part of the AHP process, the raw comparison matrix was normalized to derive ratio scale priority vectors. Normalization was achieved by dividing each value in a criterion's column by the sum of the column. This converted the comparisons to a proportional ratio scale while maintaining their relativity. The normalization process was applied to each column of the comparison matrix. It enabled priority vectors to be extracted that represented the relative weights or priorities of each criterion proportional to the others.

The normalized comparison matrix retained the original criteria relationships while transforming values to a 0 to 1 scale suitable for quantifying the relative importance or weight of each factor in the suitability analysis.

The consistency of judgments in the AHP comparison matrix was evaluated to ensure logical, high-quality criteria weights. Consistency was measured by first calculating a consistency index (CI) for the matrix. CI indicates the level of consistency in the comparisons, with lower values being more consistent.

CI was compared to a random index (RI) based on the number of criteria, to derive a consistency ratio (CR). [24] established that CR should be less than 0.1 to indicate acceptable consistency.

A consistency table was generated showing the CI, RI and CR values. If CR exceeded 0.1, the most inconsistent judgments were identified and the comparisons were revised to improve consistency.

This consistency evaluation ensured that irrational or random comparisons did not propagate into the final AHP weights. Logical, high-quality judgments translated to reliable, data-driven criteria priorities for the suitability analysis. The consistency table provided quantitative verification that the AHP process produced a consistent, robust weighting of factors for the oil spill index map.

$$\sum_{j=1}^n (N_{ij} * Weight_j) \tag{6}$$

- Weighted Sum Value i: Weighted sum for criterion i.
- Nij: Normalized value for the pairwise comparison between criteria i and j.
- Weight j: Weight for criterion j.
- n: Number of criteria.

$$\text{Principal eigenvalue } (\lambda_{\max}) = \frac{\text{Sum(Weighted Sum of each Criterion)}}{\text{Normalized Weight}} \tag{7}$$

$$C.I = \frac{\lambda_{\max} - n}{n - 1} \tag{8}$$

$$\text{Formula: } C.R = \frac{C.I}{R.I} \tag{9}$$

C.I: Consistency Index. λ_{\max} : Principal eigenvalue of the matrix, n: Number of criteria.

Table 4. Random Index Matrix of the Same Dimension

Number of criteria	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
RI	0.00	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49	1.51

Source: [24]

Table 5. Comparison Matrix for the Indices

Pairwise	NDVI	NDWI	NDBI	LST	
NDVI	1	3	5	3	3.00
NDWI	1/3	1	3	1	1.33
NDBI	1/5	1/3	1	1/3	0.47
LST	1/3	1	3	1	1.33
	1.87	5.33	12.00	5.33	

Normalized	NDVI	NDWI	NDBI	LST	Weight
NDVI	0.54	0.56	0.42	0.56	0.52

NDWI	0.18	0.19	0.25	0.19	0.20
NDBI	0.11	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.08
LST	0.18	0.19	0.25	0.19	0.20
					1.00

Consistency	NDVI	NDWI	NDBI	LST	Weighted Sum	
NDVI	0.52	0.60	0.39	0.60	2.12	4.08
NDWI	0.17	0.20	0.24	0.20	0.81	4.04
NDBI	0.10	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.32	4.02
LST	0.17	0.20	0.24	0.20	0.81	4.04
Max	4.08					

C.I	0.01					
Consistency Ratio	0.02					

The normalized indices were combined using a weighted summation approach. Each index was multiplied by its corresponding weight and results were summed using the raster calculator tool to obtain a single composite index representing the oil spill potential for the different years.

The basic formula used in computing the oil spill index *OSI* based on the weighted combination of the normalized indices was:

$$OSI = wNDVI \times NDVI + wNDWI \times NDWI + wLST \times LST + wNDBI \times NDBI \quad (10)$$

Where: *wNDVI*, *wNDWI*, *wLST*, and *wNDBI* are the weights assigned to each index.

NDVI, NDWI, LST, and NDBI are the normalized values of NDVI, NDWI, LST, and NDBI, respectively.

The validation of the Oil Spill Index (OSI) against historical oil spill incident points plays a crucial role in assessing the accuracy and reliability of the index in predicting and identifying areas prone to oil spills. The oil spill index was validated against known oil spill incident points obtained from Shell Plc. Joint investigation reports (<https://www.shell.com.ng/sustainability/environment/oil-spills/spill-incident-data.html>) website. This was to assess its accuracy and reliability. In doing this the study ensured spatial alignment between the oil spill index map and historical oil spill incident data by projecting both datasets to a common coordinate system.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Result of Normalized Difference Vegetative Index (NDVI)

Figures 3 present the NDVI maps for the years 2003, 2013, and 2023, revealing notable trends in vegetation health and density. In 2003, NDVI values ranged from -0.12 to 0.68, expanding to -0.19 to 0.76 in 2013, and narrowing to -0.17 to 0.63 in 2023. Low NDVI values typically indicate areas with sparse vegetation cover or stressed vegetation. While High NDVI values generally indicate areas with dense and healthy vegetation cover. Consistent dense vegetation was observed in the western part of the study area across all three years, contrasting with a decline in vegetation cover in the eastern part, which happens to be the part where most oil spill incidents occurred in the study area, particularly between 2013 and 2023. Analysis of oil spill points reveals a decrease generally in NDVI from 2003 to 2023, emphasizing the environmental impacts of oil spills.

Figure 3. Normalized Difference Vegetative Index (NDVI) for year 2003, 2013 and 2023

An examination of the temporal dynamics of NDVI, NDWI, LST, and NDBI indices revealed that in 2003, NDVI values ranged from -0.12 to 0.68, expanding to -0.19 to 0.76 in 2013, and narrowing to -0.17 to 0.63 in 2023 while for NDWI, in 2003, the range was from -0.56 to 0.19, in 2013 from -0.64 to 0.31, and in 2023 from -0.52 to 0.29. The NDBI range was from -0.48 to 0.39 in 2003, followed by -0.48 to 0.29 in 2013, and -0.44 to 0.31 in 2023. While, the land surface temperature values in 2003 ranged from 17.63 to 31.78°C, expanding to 20.07 to 34.21°C in 2013, and then narrowing to 18.52 to 30.4°C in 2023. The result indicates that there was a reduction in NDVI and NDWI ranges over the years, coupled with fluctuations in NDBI and LST values, reflecting significant environmental changes.

Result of the Oil Spill Index

Figure 4. Oil Spill for the Year 2003, 2013 and 2023

Source: Author's work 2023

Figure 4 represents the result of the oil spill in the study area for the years 2003, 2013 and 2023 respectively. The observed trends in the oil spill index between the years 2003 to 2013 and 2003 to 2023 revealed significant changes in oil spill susceptibility over time. From no point of spill in 2003 to four areas in the North Eastern ward in 2013, to fifteen areas spreading in the South Eastern ward in 2023, the oil spill index between 2003 and 2013 shows a mix of increases and a little decrease in oil spill susceptibility across different regions while the oil spill index trend from 2003 to 2023 indicates a substantial increase in the oil spill index over the two-decade period. This drastic rise in the oil spill index suggests a worsening of environmental conditions or an escalation in factors contributing to oil spill risks across the study area.

CONCLUSION

In assessing the impact of oil spills and mapping environmental changes in the study area, a comprehensive oil spill index map revealed higher and increased index values observed at locations with documented spill incidents leveraging on the combined power of remote sensing data and spatial analysis techniques to enhance the understanding of oil spill dynamics and vulnerability assessment. A joint force of NDVI, NDWI and NDBI has contributed to assessing the pattern and trend of oil spill in the study area. The observed trends in the oil spill revealed significant changes in oil spill susceptibility over time. From a mix of increases and a little decrease in oil spill susceptibility to a substantial increase in the oil spill index over the two-decade period thus suggesting a worsening of environmental conditions or an escalation in factors contributing to oil spill risks across the study area. The approach has been a more effective strategy for assessing and mitigating the impacts of oil spills, ultimately fostering environmental sustainability and resilience in the face of evolving environmental threats.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study is recommended as valuable information for monitoring and assessing the environmental impact of oil spills as it shows the likelihood of the study area being damaged by oil spills as the year progresses. The research recommends the contemporary data collection and presentation technique used in this research for other environmental-related issues, especially over a large region or inaccessible locations for effective response and mitigation purposes. Additionally, this study suggests a continuous environmental assessment being conducted periodically to checkmate environmental protection, the safety of the inhabitants of the location and for improvement in oil spill responses. While the current research focused on the integration of environmental indices, future studies should consider incorporating socio-economic factors to provide a more holistic understanding of oil spill risks. This may include factors such as population density, infrastructure vulnerability, economic activities, and community resilience, which play a significant role in shaping the impacts and responses to oil spills. A prompt attention to these recommendations will guarantee an understanding of oil spill dynamics, improved risk assessment methodologies that will enhance preparedness and response capabilities to mitigate the environmental, social, and economic impacts of oil spills effectively.

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